

Curvilinear-tree-ring measurements in archaeological wood samples from X-ray computed tomography

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ABSTRACT

In this paper X-ray computed tomography imaging data is used to perform nondestructive tree-ring width measurements in three archaeological wooden samples. Measurements of the curvilinear-tree-ring widths are performed using two approaches: firstly, measuring manually the distance between two points on two consecutive tree-rings along two orthogonal radii and, secondly, using a recently proposed computational approach which averages all calculated pairwise radial distances between two consecutive tree-rings along the whole tree-ring profile. The results show that the irregularity of the tree-ring shape is an important factor to be considered in performing curvilinear-tree-ring measurements. For irregular shaped tree-rings, deviations up to 1.15 mm were observed between the output of both measurement's approaches. It is concluded that tree-ring width measurements along only two orthogonal radial rays are not always accurate enough and therefore averaging along the whole tree-ring profile is recommended.

1. Introduction

Dendrochronology is a well-established method for dating archaeological wooden finds and, therefore, an essential tool for archaeological, or in a broader sense, wooden cultural heritage research (Baillie, 2002; Edvardsson et al., 2021). By measuring tree-ring widths (TRWs) series, valuable chronological and environmental data can be obtained which can be used for wooden objects dating, for the provenance determination of the wood and to reconstruct climate variability, among other applications (Visser, 2021; Cufar et al., 2015; Anchukaitis et al., 2013; Fonti et al., 2010).

Tree-ring measurements in archaeological wooden objects have been generally performed by analysing the external sample surface and manually, i.e., one-by-one, using appropriated devices (Schweingruber, 1988; Speer, 2010). Those methods, however, are limited to the information provided by the surface, which requires treatments prior any measurement to remove impurities and unevenness and to increase the contrast between early and late wood (Bräcker, 2002). Moreover, the sample surface needs to be perpendicularly oriented to the ring growth direction to avoid bias in the measurements (Van den Bulcke et al.,

2014). As a consequence, the accuracy of the results are surface-treatment dependent and therefore, these methods fail in cases where the surface is coated with materials such as lacquer or paint, or when the degree of deterioration is such that it is impossible to clearly measure the tree-rings (Sass and Eckstein, 1994). In such cases, destructive sampling practices like core drilling have to be employed to provide visual access to internal sections of the wood, from which TRW perpendicular to the trunk can be measured (Kuniholm, 2001). Inevitably these practices might lead to significant damage to the samples analysed, thus lacking applicability in unique or highly degraded archaeological wooden finds where subsamples of the wood core are impossible or not allowed to be extracted.

Among the non-destructive methods currently available, X-ray computed tomography (XCT) is a powerful imaging technique that allows to inspect the entire volume of the sample at different spatial resolutions (Carmignato et al., 2018). In addition to be non-invasive, it also requires almost no sample preparation and enables both qualitative and quantitative three-dimensional (3D) tree-ring analysis (Van den Bulcke et al., 2014; Martinez-Garcia et al., 2021). For these reasons, XCT has made great progress as a leading non-destructive microscopic technique

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in the field of dendrochronology.

Based on industrial XCT, Okochi et al. (2007) succeeded in resolving TRWs in ring-porous Japanese Oak and diffuse-porous Japanese Beech. Keefer et al. (2006) imaged annual tree-rings of three oak wood Celtic cult figures which were dated to 127 BCE (± 10 years). Grabner et al. (2009) managed to resolve TRWs down to 0.12 mm in a bronze-age wooden tool. The dendrochronology of wood in blocks of soil was explored with XCT, enabling the dating of fragments of oak (AD 500: no waney edge) (Stelzner and Million, 2015). Van den Bulcke et al. (2014) scanned Scots pine, Oak, and Teak samples with helical XCT and measured their corresponding TRWs exploiting the 3D nature of the XCT imaging data. Kastner et al. (2010), Grabner et al. (2009), Bill et al. (2012) and Stelzner and Million (2015) have all reported on the limits of the measurability of year ring widths using XCT measurements. However some challenges are still present, particularly when attempting to measure TRWs in waterlogged and conservant-impregnated archaeological wood samples, due to the low contrast found between the conserving agents and the wood matrix (Bill et al., 2012) and the radial growth anisotropy present in wood samples responsible for the occurrence of irregular shaped annual tree-rings (Sellier and Ségura, 2020).

In this work, the impact of the irregular shape of tree-rings on TRW measurements is addressed. To this aim, a recently proposed approach that automatically recognises the entire tree-ring profiles from XCT imaging data (Martinez-Garcia et al., 2021), is here applied to calculate TRWs in three archaeological wooden samples. The results are compared with those obtained from manual measurements in two dimensional (2D) XCT slices.

2. Materials and methods

Three archaeological wooden samples listed in Table 1, were analysed in this work. These samples belong to a reference collection at the Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum, Leibniz Forschungsinstitut für Archäologie, Mainz, Germany (RGZM). The collection encompasses a total of 800 wooden archaeological samples collected from different sites, which between 2008 and 2010 were conserved with different conservation methods at different institutions. A detailed overview of the conservation methods and the samples is given on the project homepage ("www.rgzm.de/kur", 2022).

The tomographic analysis was performed on the in-house a laboratory XCT system (Diondo d₂, Germany). An optimised setup and acquisition protocol for the XCT measurements was developed for conserved wood. The measurements were conducted by setting the X-ray source XWT-225 TCHE+ from X-RAY WorX, Garbsen, Germany in high power mode and choosing an acceleration voltage of 80 kV and a tube current of 300 μ A with a 1 mm aluminum filtration. The wood samples were mounted in a sample holder and placed in the climatized sample chamber. The sample was rotated by 360 degrees in continuous mode during the acquisition. The radiographical projections were recorded with an X-ray detector 4343 DX-I from Varex, Salt Lake City, U. S.A., with a pixel size of 139 μ m. The distance between the X-ray source and the sample and between the X-ray source and the detector were 160 mm and 860 mm respectively, giving a magnification of 5.37 and a nominal voxel size of 26 μ m. A total of 3000 projections images were acquired during the sample rotation of 360°. The resulting projections were converted into 3D image stacks of approx. 3008 \times 3008 \times 5910 voxels using the CERA reconstruction software based on the filtered back projection Feldkamp algorithm (Feldkamp et al., 1984) from

Table 1
Overview of the archaeological wooden samples used in this work.

Label	Wood Specie	Conservation Method	Dimension (cm) L, \varnothing
V27-10	Oak	Silicone oil	12-14, 5-6
V27-07	Oak	Kauramin 800	12-14, 5-6
V27-40	Oak	Alcohol-ether-resin	12-14, 5-6

Siemens.

Image cross-sections of the wood samples were visualised in VGStudioMax3.3© software. All algorithms used in this contribution were implemented in Python 3.7, supported by tools provided by the open-source image processing libraries scikit-image and OpenCV.

3. Results and discussion

Figure (1) shows transversal XCT cross-sections of the examined samples. As it can be seen from the figure, tree-rings and some other anatomical features, such as vessels, rays and cell collapses are clearly distinguishable in all cases. Owing to the low absorption of X-rays by the Kauramin 800 and Alcohol-ether-resin conservation agents, tree-rings can even be clearer visualised in samples V27-07 and V27-40, as ring-porous along the earlywood large vessels.

A common characteristic of all examined samples is the presence of a radial growth anisotropy, which is responsible for the occurrence of irregular-shaped annual tree-rings. As a consequence, each particular TRW displays a direction dependent magnitude, i.e., a radial variability along the whole tree-ring profile, which needs to be properly accounted in order to get accurate TRW values.

Manual TRW measurements were conducted for each wood sample by measuring the distance between two points at adjacent rings along the radial direction, i.e., direction pointing from the pith to the bark. The measurements were performed along two orthogonal radial directions using the software VG StudioMax3.3© and the results were averaged later on. The obtained results are displayed in Figure (1) and listed in Table (2), for each wood sample.

The manual TRW-measurement method described above, has the drawback that the measurements derived from it depend strongly of the choice of the two orthogonal radial directions. To overcome this issue and providing more accurate results, it would be necessary to perform TRW measurements along a significantly large number of radial directions, a task that is extremely difficult to be done manually.

To account for all possible radial directions in the TRW measurements, a recently proposed approach which is capable to recognise tree-rings and to calculate automatically TRW distances from volumetric XCT image data, was here employed. The approach basically enables to extract first the tree-rings coordinates from the XCT slices and to use this data later on, to calculate TRW distance between all detected pair of points located at consecutive tree-rings (Martinez-Garcia et al., 2021).

The successful application of this method to the present case study, required to map first the Cartesian pixel coordinates of each XCT slice, (x, y) , to Polar coordinates, (r, θ) , centred at the location (x_0, y_0) of the pith, according to:

$$(x, y) \rightarrow (\rho, \theta) \tag{1}$$

$$r = \sqrt{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2} \tag{2}$$

$$\theta = \arctan2[(x - x_0), (y - y_0)], \tag{3}$$

where r denotes the magnitude of the vector pointing from the pith to the pixel located at $(x - x_0, y - y_0)$, i.e., the radial direction, and θ the orientation of the radial vector with respect to the positive x -axis. Consequently, the pairwise Euclidean distance, TRW_{ij} , defining the distance between two points located at adjacent tree-rings with coordinates (r_i, θ) and (r_j, θ) , i.e., lying along the same radial direction, \hat{r} , with orientation θ , was mapped to Polar coordinates as:

$$TRW_{ij} = \sqrt{r_i^2 + r_j^2 - 2r_i r_j}. \tag{4}$$

For each examined sample, the plots in Figure (2) display the automatically calculated pairwise TRW_{ij} distances between two consecutive tree-rings, for all detected radial directions along the whole tree-ring profiles. It should be noted that in almost all the cases, thousands of

Figure 1. X-ray CT cross-sections of the three archaeological wooden samples. The orthogonal green lines indicate the directions along which manual measurements of the tree-ring widths were measured.

Table 2

Comparison of manual and automatic TRW measurements for each wood sample. The degree of agreement is measured with the Mean Error (ME), the root mean square error (RMSE) and the variance, $VAR = RMSE^2 - ME^2$, metrics.

Wood Samples	TRW No.	TRW [mm] Manual			TRW [mm] Automatic		Std
		Rad.1	Rad.2	Avg.	Avg.		
V27-10	1	4.20	4.29	4.25	3.87	0.58	
	2	4.68	4.64	4.66	4.18	0.49	
	3	1.37	1.81	1.59	1.39	0.42	
	4	3.93	2.63	3.28	3.19	0.42	
	ME = -						
	0.309						
	RMSE =						
	0.358						
V27-07	5	2.36	2.11	2.24	1.99	0.58	
	6	2.56	1.98	2.27	2.23	0.41	
	7	3.01	2.94	2.98	2.43	0.49	
	8	2.94	3.10	3.02	2.53	0.41	
	..						
	1	3.76	3.63	3.69	3.45	0.32	
	2	3.63	3.52	3.58	3.10	0.42	
	3	3.98	3.23	3.60	3.75	0.73	
	4	2.77	1.75	2.26	2.61	0.82	
	ME =						
0.238							
V27-40	5	1.83	1.64	1.73	1.98	0.60	
	6	1.62	2.38	2.00	3.15	0.45	
	7	1.30	1.41	1.35	1.28	0.37	
	8	1.46	0.94	1.20	2.21	0.35	
	9	0.75	0.61	0.68	0.80	0.32	
	10	-	0.50	0.50	0.61	0.27	
	..						
	1	5.06	3.82	4.44	4.63	0.55	
	2	4.65	3.06	3.85	3.91	0.54	
	3	1.15	0.84	0.99	1.39	0.56	
4	2.25	2.94	2.59	2.74	0.57		
ME =							
0.114							
V27-40	5	1.32	1.79	1.55	1.82	0.61	
	6	1.73	2.47	2.10	1.98	0.46	
7	1.94	2.65	2.29	2.08	0.39		
8	1.94	2.46	2.20	2.37	0.62		

radial directions (i.e., radii) were considered in the calculations, provided by the extensive tree-ring-coordinates dataset detected by the approach. Just in the case of the closest rings to the pith (TRW₁ in the figure), between 600 and 900 radii were considered, depending on the sample analysed. This approach provides good statistics to guarantee the

convergence of the corresponding TRW average values, which are represented by horizontal dotted lines in the plots and listed in the fourth column of Table (2).

A comparison between automated and manual TRW measurements is illustrated in Table (2) and Figure (3). The best match was obtained for the sample V27-40, where deviations between 0.06 and 0.40 mm (2 – 15 pixels) were obtained, which is confirmed with the lowest RMSE and ME metrics values. In this case, the choice of the orthogonal axis for manual measurements, as illustrated in Figure (1), was enough to account for the radial TRW variability and therefore, to yield accurate results. It should be stressed, however, that a different choice of the orthogonal axes might lead to different results. It is worth also underlining, that in both TRW measurements approaches a common x-y coordinate reference system was used, which is represented in Figure (2).

In samples V27-10 and V27-07, on the other hand, the agreement between manual and automated measurements was not good enough and deviations up to 1.15 mm, which is equivalent to 44 pixels, were observed at some irregular shaped tree-rings (e.g., TRW₆ in sample V27-07).

The oscillatory behaviour of the pairwise TRW distances in Figure (2), arises as a response to the existing radial growth anisotropy present in the samples. The wider the TRW values are spread out, the large the radial TRW variability and thus the higher the degree of radial growth anisotropy. Therefore, the amount of dispersion in the TRW data provides a measure of the degree of the radial anisotropy, which is here quantified, through the mean absolute percentage deviation metric (MAPE) as:

$$MAPE = \frac{100\%}{n} \sum_i^n \frac{\sigma_{TRW_i}}{\langle TRW \rangle_i} \tag{5}$$

where n is the total number of consecutive ring pairs and σ_{TRW_i} is the standard deviation associated to the average TRW of the i th rings pair, $\langle TRW \rangle_i$.

The computed MAPE values for the samples were found to be higher than 10%, indicating a significant degree of radial anisotropy, in particular, for the sample V27-07 where a maximum value of 24.9% was found. These results deviate notably from those reported recently for modern wood samples exhibiting fairly straight tree-rings, which did not exceed the 4% (Martinez-Garcia et al., 2021).

The described results confirm that for irregular shaped tree-rings, TRW obtained by averaging numerous measurements along the whole tree-ring profile provides a more realistic TRW-estimate than considering only few radii. It is worth underlining that, although the proposed method has been used only in archaeological wood finds, it can also be applied to other wood samples with irregular ring growth, for example,

Figure 2. Automatic measurement of pairwise TRW distances between two consecutive rings, RW_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ for all detected radial directions at each wood sample. The pair of consecutive rings are counted starting from the center as illustrated on the XCT slices. The horizontal dotted line in the plots denotes the average TRW value. The detected tree-rings positions are highlighted in red on the respective XCT slice, where the coordinate reference systems are also shown.

Figure 3. Average width of the tree rings calculated over a large number of radial directions along the whole tree-ring profile (automated approach) and over two arbitrarily chosen orthogonal direction (manual method). The length of the bars around the points corresponds to the magnitude of the standard deviation.

from geomorphologically disturbed sites of tropical tree species (Stoffel and Bollschweiler, 2008; Worbes, 2002). On the other hand, it can be also equally applicable to 2D images obtained from any other imaging technique based on different interaction mechanisms of measurement with the wood (e.g. Neutron-CT, MRI and UV microscopy) as far as good contrast between early and late wood regions is achieved. The impact of this alternative TRW-measurement method on the samples cross-dating is currently under study and will be addressed in future works.

4. Conclusions

Manual and automated averaged TRW measurements were performed in curvilinear tree-rings from three archaeological wooden samples impregnated with different conserving agents, using XCT imaging data. It was shown that manual measurements taken along only two orthogonal directions are not always enough to provide accurate TRW results, and deviations up to 1.15 mm can be expected.

The employed automated TRW measurement approach, by considering a significantly large number of radial directions along the entire ring profile, and thus considering the whole radial TRW variability, provides more accurate TRW results. In addition to that, it can also be used to quantify radial growth anisotropy of the sample. Therefore it is proposed as powerful tool for accurate TRW measurements in wood samples with irregular shaped tree-rings.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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